

THE PROBLEM AND SOLUTION OF USING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF VETERINARY STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185519>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the problem and solution of the use of English language teaching technologies in the development of professional competencies of veterinary students. The author analyzes various technologies for improving the effectiveness of teaching English.*

Keywords: *professional competence, veterinary medicine, education, English.*

On the way to building a new Uzbekistan, great changes are taking place in many areas of society's development, including in the field of higher education. In the conditions of informatization and globalization of society, new requirements are imposed on its study, new opportunities for obtaining knowledge appear, especially new approaches to teaching foreign languages, especially English. In this sense, the possibilities of using social networks in teaching students English to gain new knowledge and improve their knowledge are limitless.

Due to globalization and high rates of development of world science, the use of terminology is necessary and significant for the successful professional activity of a practicing veterinarian. In order to integrate into the international space and exchange experience, mastering the terminology system in English is necessary both for understanding and writing specialized scientific publications, and for carrying out oral professional foreign language activities.

It is necessary to take into account the factor of holding international conferences, symposiums, congresses, where, as a rule, English is a means of intercultural communication in the field of professional activity. For the effective and high-quality solution of work tasks in veterinary activities, future specialists need specialized knowledge and skills, which are commonly called professional competencies.

Ensuring the possibility of effective communication in the field of professional activity, as well as the formation of professional competencies aimed at the practical use of the English language as a tool for the realization of professional interests is the main goal of the pedagogical activity of an English teacher in the framework of secondary vocational education (SPE).

The achievement of this goal by the teacher is possible through increasing the motivation for learning English, the formation of skills and culture of professional communication, the development of the ability to navigate in the flow of foreign periodicals; the creation of a lexicon of a specialist in the professional field; preparation for future professional activity, the formation of oral speech skills, the formation of professional competence, the introduction of information technologies into the educational process.

A foreign language acts as a means and as a tool, the basis for the formation of professional competencies. This is the specificity of the formation of professional competencies in the process of learning English by students of the vocational school. In oral and written scientific veterinary

texts, operating with a terminological apparatus is mandatory. One of the most important elements of the system of professional training of specialists in vocational education institutions is teaching a foreign language. First of all, this is due to the expansion of international economic ties, an increase in the number of enterprises and partner firms, the development of information technologies and global computer networks and the increasing use of imported equipment and foreign technologies in the practice of enterprises. In this regard, there is an increasing need for specialists who speak a foreign language and are able to carry out effective professional activities in the field of international cooperation. A competence-oriented approach to learning English is particularly important in the modern world, as it provides for the formation of students' ability to communicate in a foreign language in specific professional, business, scientific fields and situations, taking into account the peculiarities of professional competencies.

If we consider a foreign language as a means of forming the professional orientation of a future specialist, it should be noted that when studying professionally oriented language material, a certain connection is established between the student's desire to acquire special knowledge and the success of language acquisition. A foreign language is an effective means of professional and social orientation.

According to the specific ratio of knowledge and skills, the discipline "Foreign Language" occupies an intermediate position between theoretical and applied disciplines of professional training, since a foreign language requires the same large amount of skills and abilities as practical disciplines, but at the same time no less knowledge than theoretical sciences. In order to successfully carry out professional orientation, it is necessary to clearly formulate the goals of foreign language speech activity, which should be socially and professionally directed.

Professional orientation in teaching a foreign language is carried out in the process of speech activity: reading, oral and written speech. To read texts in the specialty, knowledge of special vocabulary is necessary. That is why it is especially important that students master the professional vocabulary to the fullest. The teacher should conduct a professional selection of lexical material taking into account a particular specialization.

As a result of teaching a professional language, students of vocational education and training should master the specifics of reading and translating professional literature. To do this, it is necessary to read educational texts, mandatory exercises aimed at fixing vocabulary, reading with a general coverage of the content and with elements of analysis.

Motivation and the personal conscious need of students of vocational education are the basis for successful teaching of a foreign language as an academic discipline. In order to achieve high motivation of students, it is important to integrate a foreign language with special disciplines as much as possible. Such integration helps the student to master a foreign language more successfully, because when a student is well prepared in special disciplines in his native language, he has fewer difficulties in a foreign language.

With the competence-oriented professional training of students in a foreign language, the foundations of language and speech competencies are formed, allowing them to use a foreign language to obtain professionally significant information through different types of reading.

Also, communicative competence is being formed, which allows participating in written and oral professional communication in a foreign language; socio-cultural competence, which ensures effective participation in communication with representatives of other cultures. In order to achieve high learning results and effective learning of English, it is necessary to focus on the

importance of the studied educational material, on the possibility of its further use in practice and further in professional activity.

The development of listening and speaking skills in a foreign language, taking into account professional training and the scope of the language in future professional activity, forms professional competencies. Awareness of the need to implement a multi-level approach in teaching is achieved through the analysis of the process of teaching a foreign language, the content of educational texts, assignments, exercises, as well as the organization of forms and methods of educational activities. Thus, an individual language acquisition route is brought to the fore, the main goal of which is to form a positive motivation to learn English.

It is possible to determine how well the professional competencies of veterinary students are formed by the following indicators: readiness for speech foreign language activity and for creative self-realization within the framework of professional activity (which indicates a high level of motivation to learn English), the ability to use information technology in language learning, proficiency in lexical units of professional orientation.

According to S.A. Yakovleva, "veterinary terminology is a system of standardized designations based on the interrelation of named concepts manifested in the process of communicative and cognitive activity in this field of scientific activity." E.Y. Yesenina in the study presents methods of studying and systematization of terminology in the theory of pedagogical science and vocational education. E.A. Vaseeva focuses on the fact that the term, in fact, is the "semantic core" of scientific communication, denoting the concepts of the scientific field. The author notes that the term is directly related to a specific field of activity.

According to the definition of A.A. Reformatsky, the term is "a special word limited by its special purpose; a word striving to be unambiguous, as an exact expression of concepts and names of things." At the same time, the term, being a structural and functional unit of the language subsystem, describes the scope of activity and a specific scientific field, in this case, veterinary science. We believe that the terminological apparatus of a certain branch of science is the result of comprehension and synthesis, analysis of facts and processes of research works, which are a rational expression of the degree of ordering of terminological material organized into a terminological system, which is a "specific layer", which by a number of its main characteristics (structural-semantic, word-formation and stylistic) differs from common vocabulary.

Analysis of veterinary medicine terms has shown that most of the special words have Latin and ancient Greek roots. One of the oldest languages in the world is Latin. At the moment, no state speaks this language, so it is called a "dead" language, but it is actively used in natural sciences. It is the Latin language that underlies the systematization of the plant and animal world, recipes are written in this language, it is used in scientific communities as a single recognized language of nomenclature and systematics of plants, animals, as well as for describing the human body. Its significance for science is determined by two main factors: on the one hand, it bears obvious similarities with a large number of European languages in which active publication activities are carried out in the world of science and popular scientific media, and not only within the framework of natural sciences.

On the other hand, it is the fact that this language is dead and has not been developing for a long time that stabilizes the semantic content of terms, allowing us to adequately perceive not only foreign—speaking contemporaries, but also the works of scientists from an earlier period of scientific research. H.Z. Bagirokov believes that the significant role of the Latin language and its

functioning until the time of the Second World War, as universal for understanding, is associated with a broad policy of conquest and the development of anatomical science in the Roman Empire. Latin has been the official language for a long time, which acted as a means of describing unique anatomical studies. In the same period, II century BC, bilingualism begins to form, defined as follows: "bilingualism comes from the Latin word bilingual —bi — two and lingua — language, that is, bilingualism."

In the XX and XXI centuries, the priority is determined by the world scientific bilingualism, and possibly multilingualism for the purpose of information exchange. Following H.Z. Bagirokov, we conduct a comparative analysis of the functioning of the Latin and English languages in the XX and XXI centuries, the significance of which is determined in the intercultural communication of the scientific community. English is the native language of 500 million people in 12 countries, and the total number of native speakers is close to 850 million, which allows it to be defined as performing the functions of *lingua franca* in the scientific community.

Yu.Yu. Timkina defines the openness of terminology Terminology and terminological system, therefore scientific achievements in English-speaking countries influence the formation and development of veterinary terminology around the world. Thus, we consider it relevant to study veterinary terminology in English-language sources that illustrate the use of Latin simultaneously with English modern terms. The purpose of this article is to classify veterinary terms in English, which will allow to organize and systematize knowledge for a higher level of English proficiency by veterinarians. This study uses methods such as analysis, comparison and classification of terms illustrating the subject area. In linguistic science, there are previously developed classifications of veterinary terms. E.A. Vaseeva suggests considering the following groups: general scientific, attracted (from other fields), basic and proprietary terms.

According to I.Y. Apalko, it is advisable to distinguish general scientific, denoting abstract concepts, intersectoral, sectoral and highly specialized terms. The most successful, we believe, is the classification proposed by Yu.Yu. Timkina. According to the author's research, three groups of veterinary terms in English should be distinguished: general (general scientific); basic; own (highly specialized). General scientific terms include the following: adaptation — adaptation, adaptation; phenomenon — phenomenon, phenomenon; paradigm — the paradigm; structure — structure; agent — agent, acting force, factor; criterion — attribute, criterion; method — method; analysis — analysis, etc. Basic terms are represented by words common with related disciplines. According to L.N. Komarova, this group is heterogeneous, as a result of which it can be divided into three subgroups: medical, anatomical and biological terms, we distinguish the same groups in the field of veterinary medicine:

Examples of basic terms are the following words: hyperthermia — hyperthermia, fever, fever; tumor — tumor, neoplasm; viral disease — viral disease; angioma — angioma, a benign tumor developing from blood vessels; biopsy — biopsy, in vivo collection of material (tissue sample) for histological examination; anabiosis — anabiosis, reversible suppression of vital functions, hibernation; adenoma — adenoma, a benign tumor from the glandular epithelium;

meta bolic disease — заболевание обмена веществ;

zoonotic disease — зоонозная болезнь; diagnosis — диагноз, распознавание болезни; allergy — аллергия, реакция гиперчувствительности.

К базовым анатомическим терминам (животных и человека) следует отнести следующие:

thorax — грудная клетка; rumen — рубец (первый отдел желудка жвачных животных);

reticulum — сетка (второй отдел желудка жвачных животных); abomasums — сычуг (четвертый отдел желудка жвачных животных);

spinal cord — позвоночный

столб; lymph — лимфа; joint — сустав; gallbladder — желчный пузырь;

lungs — легкие;

pericardium — перикард и прочие. Биологические термины включают ботанические и зоологические термины: male — самец; germ — зародыш, микроб;

infertility — бесплодие, стерильность; selection — селекция; artificial selection — искусственный отбор;

feeding — feeding, etc.. This group is relatively static due to the fact that currently scientists mainly use the rules of the International Code of Botanical Nomenclature (Vienna Code), adopted by the Seventeenth International Botanical Congress in Vienna in 2005. On the one hand, as already mentioned above, these terms are words of Latin and ancient Greek origin, which, due to the similarity in pronunciation or spelling, facilitates the process of their memorization by veterinarians when studying a professionally oriented English language. On the other hand, there is a certain number of features of the formation of the plural of certain terms. However, veterinary medicine terms are often represented by proper names. It should be noted that in modern veterinary terminology they are widespread and reflect the scientific achievements of many generations of naturalists, veterinarians and scientists.

L.N. Komarova focuses on the fact that it is in eponymous terms that the main stages of the development of veterinary science are reflected. Examples are the following terminological units: Golgi complex — Golgi complex, described by Camillo Golgi in 1898; Fallopian tube — Fallopian tube, oviduct, described in the XVI century by Gabriel Fallopius; circle of Willis — Willis circle (described by English anatomist Thomas Willis); Newcastle disease — pseudocuma of birds, Newcastle disease (discovered for the first time near the city of Newcastle in 1927) and others. The process of the emergence of new eponymic terms is continuous because eponyms reflect the results of scientific discoveries and practical activities of scientists.

For example, in 2011, a new viral disease of cows was described, called Schmallenberg disease (at the place of its detection in Germany). We believe that it is advisable to determine the importance of abbreviation in the formation of terminology used in English-language veterinary science, which began functioning in natural and medical texts at the end of the XIX century, and at the beginning of the XX century its use in the scientific world in order to increase the informative value of texts became widespread. In fact, at this stage of the development of science, it is impossible to meet a work without abbreviations, which indicates the convenience and expediency of using this language tool in scientific works.

Terminology and terminology The use of abbreviations in veterinary medicine illustrates the economy of expressive means. It is necessary to note the ways of forming an abbreviation: abbreviations by the first letters (BP — blood pressure, AGRIS — Agricultural information system); abbreviations of the first element of a complex term in the presence of the full form of the main term (N-medicine — nuclear medicine); initial abbreviations, including the syllabic component of the original form (hihum — high humidity); omissions of some letters and syllables and combining initial and final letters or elements (bsh — bushel); the initial element of the first

word and part of the second word (Aq.dest — aqua destillata; Ch.cer. — charta cerata; Cont.rem. — continuantur remedia).

The problem of the formation of an abbreviation is polysemy and homonymy, since an incorrect interpretation of abbreviations can lead to an erroneous diagnosis and the appointment of the wrong drug. At the same time, it is necessary to indicate the significance of graphic abbreviations that are present in written speech. At the end of the XX century, a new method of abbreviation appeared, qualitatively different from the previously designated ones — homoacronymy, which is the creation of abbreviated units that coincide in their phonetic structure with commonly used words, since the decoding of such an abbreviation remains implicit, then in the field of veterinary medicine when working with animal case histories does not gain popularity.

Thus, the use of Latin in veterinary medicine is being transformed, is significant and in demand for the development of universal global science. Terminology with Latin roots provides an understanding of veterinary and medical vocabulary, helps to unite a wide audience into a single space for the development of world research. Methods of formation of veterinary terminology in English illustrate the lack of a unified classification of veterinary vocabulary, therefore, the classification is an open dynamic system that develops on the basis of the Latin language in accordance with modern science.

In the field of veterinary medicine, we have proposed the following classification of terms: veterinary, anatomical and biological. At the same time, due to the development of modern science and the need for scientific compression of information, current sources of replenishment of terms in the field of veterinary medicine are designated eponymous terms and abbreviations as priority sources that allow, with minimal presentation in writing, to convey the content as accurately and exhaustively as possible. Specialized terminology contributes to the systematization of the knowledge of a veterinarian and the formation of foreign-language intercultural professional competence, which is an important impetus for the further development of educational practice in the field of pedagogical terminology in the context of international cooperation and the globalization of science.

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